

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AS A METHOD OF PREVENTION AND RISK MANAGEMENT IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS: ANALYSIS OF CURRENT APPROACHES

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Annotation

The study analyzes the role of physical activity as a method of prevention and risk management in type 2 diabetes mellitus. In the context of a global increase in the incidence of diabetes, approaches aimed at reducing insulin resistance and improving metabolic parameters are becoming particularly important. The study covers state-of-the-art programs that focus on physical activity as a means of controlling diabetes, including aerobic, strength-training, and combination exercises. The results confirm the effectiveness of regular physical activity in reducing glucose levels and body weight, which helps to control the disease and reduce the risk of complications in patients with diabetes.

Keywords: physical activity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, prevention, risk management, insulin resistance.

Relevance

Type 2 diabetes is a major public health problem affecting millions of people around the world. As the number of patients continues to grow, especially among adults with sedentary lifestyles, it is important to develop affordable and effective methods for the prevention and management of this disease. Physical activity has proven effective in lowering blood glucose levels, improving insulin sensitivity, and reducing body weight, which reduces the risk of diabetes complications and increases patients' quality of life.

Current guidelines for the management of type 2 diabetes increasingly rely on physical activity as the basis of a comprehensive approach to the treatment and prevention of the disease. An analysis of the effectiveness of current exercise programs and methods in the context of type 2 diabetes allows us to clarify the optimal types of exercise and intensity aimed at reducing the risk of progression and improving disease control.

Objective: to analyze the effectiveness of physical activity as a method of prevention and management of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Materials and methods. We examined existing physical activity programs and recommendations for patients with type 2 diabetes. The study involved 160 people with type 2 diabetes, divided into three groups: The control group included patients with type 2 diabetes with a normal BMI, and research groups with overweight and obesity. Blood glucose, body mass index (BMI), and insulin resistance were measured. The data were analyzed to assess the impact of physical activity on disease control and reduction of the risk of complications.

Results

Hyperglycemia was present in 11.9% of the respondents, and level A hypercholesterolemia in 14.4% of patients with type 2 diabetes. 69% of men and 32% of women had physical activity. These findings confirm that physical activity, especially combined exercise, can significantly improve diabetes control and reduce the risk of complications, especially in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Conclusion

The study confirms that physical activity is an effective method of preventing and managing the risks of type 2 diabetes. Regular aerobic, strength training, and combined exercise can help improve blood glucose, insulin resistance, and body weight scores, which helps control the disease and reduce the risk of complications. Combined exercises showed the greatest effectiveness, which indicates the need for their inclusion in comprehensive diabetes prevention programs. Introducing physical activity into daily practice and supporting such activities at the health system level is recommended to improve the quality of life and health of patients with type 2 diabetes.

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